

12 **Abstract**

13 *Background:* Renewed efforts by the Nigerian government to address malnutrition have led to
14 nutrition actions by several sectors, including the agriculture sector. However, the success of
15 these actions depends on the characteristics of the stakeholders involved, including their
16 relationships and coordination.

17 *Objective:* This paper reports a 2015 study of nutrition-sensitive agricultural stakeholders in
18 Nigeria that assessed what the stakeholders do, where they work and how they are organised
19 to improve nutrition. The study provides a baseline for assessing progress and measuring
20 stakeholder and coordination changes in the Nigerian nutrition-sensitive agriculture landscape.

21 *Methods:* Semi-structured interviews (n = 17) and focus group discussions (n = 2) were held
22 with federal, state and local government level stakeholders; reviews of stakeholder programme
23 documents were also conducted.

24 *Results:* The study identified seven groups of nutrition-sensitive agriculture stakeholders and
25 several coordination challenges. Political leadership; advocacy and provision of material and
26 human resource support by nongovernmental organisations; and donor interest and funding;
27 have been vital for mobilising nutrition-sensitive agriculture. Still, although stakeholders
28 frequently highlighted that nutrition was an important consideration in their interventions,
29 nutrition goals and activities and/or indicators to measure outcomes were not regularly
30 communicated. Also, while coordination mechanisms existed, there appeared to be minimal
31 actual cross-sectoral partnerships because of inadequate trust, competition, and conflicts over
32 institutional turf and mandates.

33 *Conclusions:* Needed enablers for improving nutrition-sensitive agriculture in Nigeria included
34 improved stakeholder nutrition literacy, as well as enhanced stakeholder engagement

35 facilitated by role definition, clarification and consensus. Exploring different approaches to
36 coordination may also be necessary.

37 **Keywords:** Stakeholder engagement, multisectoral, co-location, capacity, enabling
38 environment, nutrition literacy

39

40 **Introduction**

41 The characteristics of stakeholders, such as their knowledge, beliefs, motives, interests and
42 values, are critical in decision making and action.¹ These characteristics can influence what
43 stakeholders perceive to be problems, how they define the issues, their preferred solutions and
44 their chosen method of implementing the solutions.²⁻⁴ Even when stakeholders are strongly
45 motivated to address a problem and are aware of best practices for solving that problem, their
46 decisions and actions are often determined by extraneous factors like their perceptions of the
47 cultural, political, social and economic environment, the position of authority, opinions of
48 revered colleagues and international pressure.^{3,5,6} Indeed, interactions between stakeholders
49 have been reported to enable or hinder the decisions and actions of stakeholders and the
50 functioning of the system to which they belong and its capacity to adapt to contextual changes.⁷
51 Coordination of stakeholders to achieve common goals has been highlighted as a necessary
52 action for enabling change.⁸⁻¹⁰ For nutrition, specifically, lack of adequate stakeholder
53 engagement and coordination has been repeatedly shown to be a significant limiting factor for
54 achieving progress in addressing malnutrition.⁸⁻¹²

55 Effective stakeholder engagement can build trust; improve productivity; minimise mistakes
56 and ineffectiveness; increase intervention scale and coverage, increase donor interest and
57 support.^{13,14} Engagement can occur at about five different levels, ranging from information
58 sharing to empowerment, depending on the perceived influence that a stakeholder has over the
59 success of an intervention (higher perceived influence requires higher levels of engagement).¹³
60 Coordination has been defined as mobilizing people, activities and material resources to work
61 together to achieve a common goal. Like stakeholder engagement, it fosters trust, advocacy,
62 and resource mobilisation, strengthens capacity, and increases efficiency and synergy.⁸⁻¹⁰

63 The nutrition-sensitive agriculture (NSA) literature highlights two types of approaches for
64 coordinating nutrition – an integration approach or a co-location approach.^{15,16} In an integration
65 approach, a single programme is designed with roles for different ministries. There is a need
66 for a lead ministry to oversee the programme activities of the other ministries involved and
67 coordinate plans, funds’ disbursement, monitoring, reporting and accounting.¹⁷ With a co-
68 location approach, nutrition programmes are not implemented as multisectoral activities but as
69 sectoral, within the same geographic location.¹⁵ Each sector independently designs and
70 implements its programme, addressing one or more of the causes of malnutrition, using its
71 structures and leadership. It is helpful but not compulsory to have a lead coordinating body.¹⁷
72 The co-location approach has been reported to be a more effective approach in the context of
73 certain countries.^{15,18,19}

74 Findings from several countries^{16,20–25} emphasise that context, including stakeholder
75 characteristics and interactions, can be a significant effect modifier for any of the pathways
76 through which agriculture can improve nutrition. While there are generally accepted NSA
77 pathways that should be addressed in the context of each country, actions that can realistically
78 be taken and actions that end up implemented depend on stakeholder attributes such as
79 leadership, knowledge, resources and willingness to act.²²

80 In Nigeria, the agricultural sector traditionally focused on food production and job and wealth
81 creation and was typically not overtly involved in promoting improved nutrition despite its
82 fundamental relevance.²⁶ At the end of 2014, an Agricultural Sector Food Security and
83 Nutrition Strategy (AFSNS)²⁷ was drafted to guide the design and implementation of actions
84 that will improve nutrition in the agriculture sector (nutrition-sensitive agriculture). This
85 AFSNS includes eight priority areas and 101 potential outputs, and mentions more than twenty
86 stakeholders that the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) would
87 need to collaborate with to achieve the AFSNS objectives. Therefore, implementing the

88 AFSNS requires a paradigm shift and coordination involving many stakeholders, including
89 those already working to improve nutrition in Nigeria.

90 Given the role that stakeholders can play in enabling or hindering action, it is necessary to
91 understand who the stakeholders for NSA in Nigeria are, what they do, where they work, how
92 they are organised to improve nutrition and existing coordination mechanisms. This
93 understanding will allow FMARD to leverage existing actions and improve coherence,
94 consistency, synergy, scale, impact and accountability among stakeholders. A study to
95 contribute to such an understanding was conducted in 2015. However, the report of this study
96 was not widely disseminated.

97 The AFSNS was formally launched in 2017, but implementation has been limited to date,
98 prompting new calls and planning for an analysis of stakeholders and bottlenecks to
99 implementation. Indeed, these calls resonate with a global need to understand the relationship
100 between contextual factors and the success and failure of NSA implementation.¹⁶ To prevent
101 duplication of efforts and provide a baseline to compare changes over time and persistent gaps,
102 this paper summarises the findings from the 2015 study of stakeholders and interventions
103 promoting improved nutrition through agriculture in Nigeria. The study also identified
104 coordination approaches, challenges and opportunities.

105 **Methods**

106 **Study context and design**

107 In 2011, Nigeria was described as having a “*nutrition-agriculture paradox*” in which food
108 security at aggregate levels is in marked contrast with high levels of undernutrition among
109 women and children. More paradoxical was that families working in the agriculture sector often
110 had the worst undernutrition.²⁸ Actions to increase agricultural production in Nigeria were

111 intensified beginning in 2011. FMARD, through the Agricultural Transformation Agenda
112 (ATA) 2011 – 2015, increased access to inputs, credit and farmer education while ensuring
113 harvest demand and supporting agricultural research and development. FMARD further
114 committed to improving nutrition in Nigeria. The Honourable Minister of Agriculture and
115 Rural Development (2011 – 2015) appointed a Senior Advisor on Food Security and Nutrition
116 and encouraged the formation of a Nutrition Transformation Value Chain (NTVC) to promote
117 greater nutrition sensitivity of agricultural policies, programmes and value chains. The NTVC
118 was a multisectoral technical working group and successfully facilitated the drafting of the
119 AFSNS.

120 Still, despite the commitment to improving nutrition, FMARD's historically passive role in
121 addressing nutrition meant that the focus on building nutrition-sensitive agricultural systems
122 required an evidence base from which action could spring; as well as a situation analysis of
123 relevant ongoing efforts that could be used to guide the contextualisation of future activity. The
124 cross-sectional mapping of stakeholders, interventions and coordination mechanisms reported
125 in this paper was conducted as part of the situation analysis. Methods used for the study
126 included document reviews, key informant interviews and focus group discussions (FGDs).
127 The proposal for the study was reviewed and approved by the Office of the Honourable
128 Minister of Agriculture in Nigeria.

129 **Data collection**

130 The study used snowball sampling to determine stakeholders (organisations) promoting
131 nutrition through agriculture in Nigeria. In-depth interviews were conducted with federal, state
132 and local government area (LGA) level key informants, and focus group discussions (FGDs)
133 were held with federal level key informants. As part of the interviews, each key informant was
134 asked to mention organisations linking agriculture to nutrition and identify a key informant

135 within the organisations mentioned. Subsequently, the websites of mentioned organisations
136 were visited and information about their programmes and activities was retrieved. Where
137 possible, interviews were held with key informants in the identified organisations to obtain
138 further information about the interventions, enablers and challenges of implementing NSA in
139 Nigeria. The organisations' programme documents were also collected. Additional
140 stakeholders were then identified through the analysis of websites and documents. Further to
141 identifying stakeholders and interventions, key informants were asked about stakeholder
142 networking and coordination and the opportunities and challenges for coordination.

143 Content was retrieved from 16 websites between February and April 2015 (Supplemental
144 Material 1) and 25 programme documents^{27,29-52} were reviewed. Seventeen (17) key informants
145 were interviewed, and two focus group discussions (FGDs) with a combined total of seven
146 participants were conducted. Across the 24 participants for both interviews and FGDs, just six
147 were not in managerial or directorship positions. Table 1 summarises the organisations of the
148 participants. Interviews and FGDs for the study were conducted between February and March
149 2015 in collaboration with the Federal Department of Agriculture at FMARD. The study was
150 conducted in adherence to the Declaration of Helsinki principles. Consent for interviews and
151 FGDs was obtained at both organizational and individual levels. Starting with FMARD,
152 organizations were approached for interviews with relevant programme staff. Oral informed
153 consent was then obtained from all key informants and participants at FGDs. Consent was
154 obtained separately for participation in the study and audio recording of interviews/FGDs.
155 Consent for both participation and audio recording was obtained for 12 interviews and the two
156 FGDs. For five interviews, key informants consented to participate but not to be audio
157 recorded; detailed notes were therefore taken at these interviews.

158 **Data analysis**

159 Interviews were transcribed, and transcripts and interview notes (where there were no
160 transcripts) were analysed according to study objectives. Content analysis of documentation
161 about programmes and activities was conducted to identify agriculture-linked-to-nutrition
162 interventions. Interventions were considered nutrition-sensitive if they included activities to
163 address the underlying causes of malnutrition (food, health and care) or the immediate causes
164 of malnutrition (dietary intake and disease). All analyses (interviews, FGDs, websites and
165 documents) were guided using templates that were developed a priori based on the study's
166 objectives. Key themes around stakeholders' NSA interests, relationships, coordination,
167 challenges and other characteristics were subsequently identified. Findings from the study and
168 ensuing recommendations were presented at a December 2015 meeting of nutrition focal
169 persons from multisectoral government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs), some
170 of whom had been participants in the study. Presented recommendations centred around actions
171 to improve stakeholder engagement and co-location as a coordination approach. The findings
172 and recommendations were discussed at the meeting and participants' reactions were
173 documented.

174 **Results**

175 **Stakeholders and interventions linking agriculture to nutrition in Nigeria**

176 Seven groups of stakeholders with agricultural interventions that had nutrition-sensitivity
177 potential were identified: government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs);
178 international non-profit organisations (INGOs); Nigerian NGOs and other organisations; the
179 United Nations (UN) system; bilateral agencies; research organisations and funding
180 organisations.

181 ***Government MDAs***

182 The primary government MDAs involved in promoting improved nutrition through agriculture
183 were several FMARD departments, the National Programme on Food Security (NPFS),
184 National Agricultural Research Institutes (NARIs), the Fadama III Project, and Agricultural
185 Development Programmes/Authorities (ADPs/ADAs) in every state of the country and the
186 Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. FMARD departments included the Departments of
187 Agriculture (trees and crops), Fisheries, Livestock, Rural Development, Agricultural
188 Extension, and Strategic Reserve. Within the Federal Department of Agriculture, a Nutrition
189 Unit had been formed out of another unit to integrate nutrition into all agricultural value chains.
190 Key nutrition-related activities within MDAs included appointment and training of nutrition
191 desk officers at federal, state and LGA levels; promotion of value chains of nutrient-dense
192 commodities; delivery of nutrition education to farming families; and research to increase the
193 nutrient content of crops and development of nutritious products from local foods. The state
194 ADPs were the primary extension and agricultural development arm of FMARD, and the ADP
195 system had mechanisms through which village extension agents (VEAs) received and
196 transferred innovations and modern technologies to farming families.

197 Some key informants were not entirely sure what activities were being conducted in their
198 department concerning nutrition. It appeared that part of the ignorance was because the
199 departments were not doing anything explicit yet. The AFSNS was still in its infancy and
200 reports of some officers suggested that their nutrition activities were assumed rather than
201 manifest. These officers equated their department's work to produce a particular food or
202 promote food security as improving nutrition. Except for NPFS, the Extension Department,
203 and the Nutrition Unit in the Agriculture Department, other departments and agencies had not
204 gone beyond the planning stage to implement nutrition-sensitive interventions.

205 ***International non-profit organisations (INGOs)***

206 Several INGOs were implementing agriculture linked to nutrition interventions in Nigeria. The
207 scale and scope of these activities and how they were related to existing governmental
208 structures usually depended on each organisation's missions and objectives.

209 ***Nigerian NGOs and other organisations***

210 Very few Nigerian NGOs, private, or research organisations were identified. This does not
211 mean that they did not exist; it just means that they were unknown or not readily recalled as
212 stakeholders at the federal level where sampling and most interviews occurred. It appeared
213 probable that Nigerian organisations promoting nutrition through agriculture conducted most
214 of their activities at the state and LGA levels and were thus known only to relevant individuals
215 working at these levels. It also appeared that Nigerian organisations' implementation of
216 nutrition-sensitive agricultural interventions was linked to extrinsic factors (such as donor
217 funding) and was therefore inconsistent.

218 ***United Nations (UN) system***

219 The central UN system funds, programmes and specialised agencies involved in promoting
220 nutrition through agriculture in Nigeria were the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO),
221 International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD), World Bank and United Nations
222 Children's Fund (UNICEF). All these organisations worked through the federal government
223 and FMARD and lent their support to the implementation and success of the ATA. FAO, IFAD
224 and the World Bank supported agriculture interventions with increasing integration of
225 nutrition. UNICEF primarily focused on nutrition interventions without any agricultural
226 components, but plans were underway to promote the use of biofortified crops in infant and
227 young child feeding.

228 ***Bilateral agencies***

229 The primary bilateral agencies involved in NSA were the UK Department for International
230 Development (DFID) – now the Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO) –
231 and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). Both organisations
232 planned and implemented NSA interventions through the help of implementing partners and
233 funded NSA projects of other organisations.

234 ***Research organisations***

235 The major research organisations working to improve nutrition through agriculture in Nigeria
236 were the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), HarvestPlus, International
237 Potato Centre (CIP) and the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). All these
238 research organisations worked in partnership with relevant NARIs. HarvestPlus, CIP and IITA
239 developed bio-fortified staple crops (such as vitamin A maize and vitamin A cassava) and
240 helped transfer the technologies to smallholder farmers. IITA also developed improved plant
241 breeding and soil, crop, pest management, and postharvest processing and storage techniques,
242 focusing on transferring the technologies, particularly to smallholder farmers. IITA generally
243 had several projects to improve agricultural production and yield in Nigeria, but not all projects
244 had explicit nutrition objectives and/or actions.

245 ***Funding organisations***

246 In addition to the World Bank, DFID and USAID already mentioned, the European Union (EU)
247 through the European Commission’s Humanitarian Aid and Civil Protection department
248 (ECHO), African Development Bank (AfDB) and Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)
249 were significant sources of funding for NSA interventions. These organisations also shaped
250 how the issue was addressed and facilitated new knowledge about effective methods through
251 requests for proposals that required innovation and ingenuity.

252 Supplemental Material 2 describes the relevant activities of the identified stakeholders in
253 greater detail and summarises interventions ongoing in 2015. Overall, efforts to link agriculture
254 to nutrition were underdeveloped. Many of the identified interventions mentioned improved
255 food security as a goal and some mentioned improved nutrition, but specific nutrition aims,
256 tools and activities were generally not mentioned. Instead, many stakeholders considered
257 improved nutrition to be a foregone conclusion of increased food production, market access,
258 and/or incomes.

259 Even for programmes that had clearly defined nutrition goals and activities, there were hardly
260 any mentions of indicators to measure progress or determine success. The components of the
261 interventions also varied in the degree to which they linked agriculture and nutrition. Some
262 interventions were primarily nutrition-focused but included agricultural components to achieve
263 nutrition objectives. Other interventions were mainly agriculture-focused but included nutrition
264 components to enhance impact. No intervention appeared to integrate agriculture and nutrition
265 fully, such that objectives, components, expected impact and indicators all included agriculture
266 and nutrition considerations. In several cases, the objectives of the interventions did not
267 explicitly include nutrition, yet improved nutrition was an anticipated impact of the
268 intervention. Further, the implementation of federal government-led interventions varied from
269 state to state and from one LGA to another within states because of the varying extent of interest
270 and political will at these levels.

271 **Coordination of nutrition activities within the agriculture sector**

272 Three different coordination mechanisms for nutrition activities within the agricultural sector
273 in Nigeria were assessed: coordination among FMARD MDAs; coordination between FMARD
274 and state and LGA level MDAs for agriculture; and coordination among FMARD, MDAs in
275 other sectors, INGOs, donors, and other organisations.

276 ***Coordination among FMARD departments and agencies (intrasectoral horizontal***
277 ***coordination)***

278 Key informants stated that some coordination exists among the different departments in
279 FMARD and with FMARD agencies. Coordination appeared to exist mainly around joint
280 meetings. Generally, each department and agency (apart from NARIs, where no interviews
281 were conducted) could provide some information about the nutrition activities conducted by
282 other departments, and some even reported having shared projects. The departments also
283 reported working closely with NARIs who developed technology that was transferred to
284 farmers. However, coordination among departments was far from perfect, as they were
285 informed but not necessarily involved. There were, in fact, duplications of efforts identified.
286 Several departments mentioned developing training manuals that would be used to train
287 extension agents and farmers about nutrition through them.

288 Similarly, two different departments claimed ownership of Home Grown School Feeding
289 Programmes (HGSFP) planned by FMARD. Further, information sharing was not universal.
290 For instance, two heads of departments (Directors) reported not knowing what was being done
291 about nutrition in other departments, even though their department also conducted nutrition
292 activities or had oversight functions. In the words of one of them: *“If you want me to be very*
293 *frank with you, coordination is very poor in terms of information, awareness, sensitisation*
294 *about the nutrition value chain in FMARD”*.

295 ***Coordination between FMARD MDAs and state and LGA agriculture MDAs (intrasectoral***
296 ***vertical coordination)***

297 State Ministries of Agriculture and Rural Development (SMARD) had departments like those
298 at the federal level. However, instead of an Agriculture Extension Department, the state ADP
299 conducted the extension activities of SMARD. The functions of the other departments, such as
300 Agriculture, Fisheries and Livestock, involved increasing agricultural participation and

301 production by creating enabling policy environments and programmes. These departments
302 carried out their functions by working with the Department of Agriculture in each LGA. The
303 LGA Department of Agriculture had officers assigned to carry out activities related to one or
304 more departments at the state level. Like the ADPs had VEAs who delivered extension
305 services, including nutrition education, to farming families, the LGAs' department of
306 agriculture also had extension services officers who performed comparable roles. In addition
307 to SMARD, there were also FMARD offices in each of the states and the FCT. These offices
308 had officers representing departments and agencies at the federal level, for example, NPFS
309 Director and ATA Director. The role of these officers was to serve as liaison officers between
310 the federal level and the state level. To ensure that programmes and activities received political
311 support at the state level and facilitated appropriate budgetary allocations, state Commissioners
312 for Agriculture and Rural Development were involved in the ATA and AFSNS through the
313 National Council of Agriculture and Rural Development (NCARD). NCARD was the highest
314 policymaking body for agriculture in Nigeria. It comprised the Honourable Minister for
315 Agriculture and Rural Development, the Minister of State, and all Honourable Commissioners
316 for Agriculture, Rural Development, and Cooperatives. Still, apart from the ADP system that
317 had historically involved nutrition activities, very little was going on in nutrition outside of the
318 federal level MDAs.

319 ***Coordination between FMARD and other sectors (multisectoral horizontal coordination)***

320 There was limited collaboration between actors in the agricultural and other sectors. The
321 nutrition sector in Nigeria was reported to have its nerve centre in the Federal Ministry of
322 Health (FMOH) Department of Family Health and the National Primary Health Care
323 Development Agency (NPHCDA). However, except for Action Against Hunger (ACF), whose
324 exact NSA interventions were not identified, none of the organisations implementing NSA

325 activities mentioned FMOH or NPHCDA or any other primarily nutrition-focused organisation
326 as partners (Supplemental Material 2).

327 The inadequate sectoral alignment in nutrition-sensitive agricultural interventions in Nigeria
328 began from the intervention design stage. The draft AFSNS produced by FMARD highlighted
329 comprehensive plans to ensure that agriculture in Nigeria is made nutrition-sensitive and
330 included a strategy framework that highlighted objectives and institutional roles. For nearly all
331 the objectives and actions listed, FMARD was assigned the responsibility of the lead agency,
332 even for actions that were already being implemented by other federal ministries and agencies.
333 The multisectoral National Plan of Action on Food and Nutrition, produced by the National
334 Planning Commission, explicitly assigned some of the actions to other MDAs. These MDAs
335 implemented the activities independently of FMARD and the agriculture sector in general.

336 In addition, key informants reported that multisectoral coordination between FMARD and
337 other ministries was traditionally poor and limited to joint attendance at meetings. The
338 establishment of the NTVC was mentioned and was considered to have improved coordination.
339 In addition to FMARD's Directors of Agriculture, Fisheries, Livestock, Extension, and
340 Planning & Coordination, and the Nutrition Desk Officer, the NTVC includes representatives
341 of FMOH, Federal Ministry of Education, Federal Ministry of Women Affairs (FMWA),
342 UNICEF, HKI, Save the Children International, GAIN, Africare Nigeria, amongst others. The
343 NTVC was successfully involved in drafting the AFSNS itself, and had held several meetings
344 and workshops to advance a nutrition agenda in the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Key
345 informants were optimistic about the new opportunities for multisectoral coordination.
346 However, they mentioned that such coordination was still challenging because it was unwieldy,
347 time-consuming, required a very committed department/agency to drive it, adequate funding
348 in all involved organisations and required regular meetings. Moreover, key informants
349 expressed concerns about the lack of such interministerial structures at the state and LGA level;

350 and about the ability of the NTVC to make a significant impact in driving the implementation
351 of the AFSNS if states were not interested and/or willing to act.

352 In addition to the NTVC, a National Committee on Food and Nutrition (NCFN) drew
353 membership from institutions/organisations comparable to that in the NTVC, including
354 FMARD. However, a significant difference was that while the NTVC members were mainly
355 bureaucratic policymakers who were career civil servants in the relevant ministries,
356 membership of the NCFN was made up of appointed (political) policymakers. NCFN also
357 included Heads of Department from leading university departments of nutrition in the country,
358 the Director Generals of the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control
359 and the Standards Organisation of Nigeria, the Executive Director of NPHCDA, and the
360 President of the Nutrition Society of Nigeria. The NCFN had its Secretariat in the National
361 Planning Commission (now Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning) and was
362 mandated to coordinate and provide leadership for multisectoral action to reduce malnutrition
363 in Nigeria. NCFN had coordination but not implementation functions and was expected to
364 influence action at the state and LGA levels through corresponding State Committees on Food
365 and Nutrition (SCFN) and Local Government Committees on Food and Nutrition (LGCFN).
366 The SCFN and LGCFN were expected to have their Secretariats in the State Planning
367 Commission and the Office of the LGA Vice Chairman, respectively.

368 **Factors that enable nutrition-sensitive agriculture interventions in Nigeria**

369 Key informants mentioned several factors that encouraged nutrition-sensitive agricultural
370 interventions. Firstly, strong political leadership, evidenced by the interest and leadership for
371 food and nutrition security shown by the then Honourable Minister of Agriculture, Dr.
372 Akinwumi Adesina, which led to the ATA and AFSNS; was a consistent, supportive factor
373 mentioned. Next was the advocacy and provision of material and human resource support by

374 INGOs and donor interest and funding. Several INGOs conducted advocacy to encourage the
375 government to mainstream nutrition into agricultural policies and plans. These INGOs and
376 some donors further facilitated the deliberation of the pertinent issues by sponsoring meetings
377 and workshops. Some key informants highlighted how their knowledge about and interest in
378 implementing NSA interventions was stimulated through participation in meetings and
379 workshops of stakeholders already implementing such interventions. In general, meetings of
380 all relevant stakeholders were considered an enabling factor.

381 Another perceived enabling factor was that government institutional arrangements existed that
382 could be used to implement and coordinate NSA interventions. The key informants gave
383 examples of structures that could be leveraged, including the National Programme for Food
384 Security and ADP system, which had a wealth of experience in implementing nutrition-linked
385 agriculture interventions, were universal to states, and had endured political, administrative
386 and donor changes. Availability of lessons from the experience of other countries that have
387 been successful in instituting NSA was further considered enabling.

388 **Challenges to nutrition-sensitive agricultural interventions in Nigeria**

389 The study's key informants stressed several challenges that hamper the ability to design and
390 implement NSA. Mainly, NSA interventions were yet to be harmonised across departments
391 and agencies in FMARD and across relevant sectors, so there was duplication of efforts. Under
392 ATA, many of the production departments and food value chains have been asked to include
393 nutrition considerations in their activities. In a bid to do so, there were undertakings in several
394 departments and units – such as the development of nutrition training materials for farmers –
395 which aimed to achieve the same purpose. However, since decisions were often taken in silos
396 (without interaction with others), the actions of departments and units were mostly unknown
397 to each other, so there was little collaboration to leverage each other's efforts and achieve

398 synergy. It was reported that there was suspicion and lack of trust among stakeholders at all
399 levels, partly due to rivalry and competition, resulting in information hoarding, narrow-focused
400 interventions and institutional turf battles, which further exacerbated policy silos.

401 Funding challenges were also considered substantial. These challenges included excessive
402 dependence on donors and the federal government for funds and other inputs; reduced
403 budgetary allocations and delays in disbursement of budgetary allocations for agriculture
404 interventions at the federal level; partial disbursement of budgetary allocations; inadequate
405 funding for nutrition activities; inadequate and lack of budgetary allocations for agriculture
406 interventions at the state and LGA levels respectively; and lack of counterpart funding at the
407 state/LGA level even when donors or the federal government were able to contribute some
408 funding. Key informants highlighted general indifference and/or lack of cooperation at the state
409 and LGA levels. States and LGAs in Nigeria have autonomy about whether to act on an issue,
410 the type of action and the degree of action. Thus, it does not matter how laudable an
411 intervention is; if the states and LGAs do not actively commit to it, nothing meaningful can be
412 accomplished and/or sustained.

413 Inadequate human resources at federal, state, and LGA levels, in terms of number, capacity,
414 and distribution of available human resources, were another major challenge. It was repeatedly
415 pointed out that the number of personnel available at different levels was inadequate to get the
416 job done. For instance, although the ADP structure intends one VEA for 1,000 farming
417 families, the reality is that some VEAs had to handle 10,000 to 20,000 farming families due to
418 an insufficient number of VEAs. One of the state ADPs reported having 170,000 farming
419 families but only 70 VEAs, rather than the 170 expected. Yet state governments were not
420 recruiting new staff because of budget constraints.

421 Moreover, the VEAs received messages about many topics and so had to contend with
422 delivering a lot of information even when they were covering only the intended number of
423 farming families. Regarding the capacity of available human resources, some key informants
424 admitted that they did not have the knowledge or training to plan for and/or implement
425 nutrition-sensitive activities. In contrast, they had been mandated to do so.

426 Coordination challenges were additionally emphasised. For intrasectoral horizontal
427 coordination, nutrition activities were fairly new to almost all the departments and agencies,
428 and even the NTVC was only recently established. Hence, there had also been little shared
429 understanding among the various departments on which to base coordination. The key
430 informants emphasised that although coordination mechanisms existed, very little coordination
431 occurs in practice. For intrasectoral vertical coordination, federal level key informants
432 expressed difficulty getting states to cooperate and support programmes and activities and
433 highlighted little to no support for multisectoral action at the state and LGA levels. Whereas
434 multisectoral coordination often received focus (even if only verbally) at the federal level, the
435 situation was perceived to be different at the lower levels. Thus, even when states and LGAs
436 decided to implement multisectoral interventions designed at the federal level, the interventions
437 were poorly executed.

438 On the other hand, state-level key informants perceived that federal level actors needed to
439 respect existing coordination structures rather than often bypassing the state offices to go to
440 the VEAs directly. State-level key informants also perceived that federal stakeholders
441 sometimes hindered the execution of planned activities by restricting information. In addition,
442 state-level informants reported that it was challenging coordinating activities with the LGA
443 departments of agriculture because they were not adequately funded by their LGAs. Hence,
444 even when the LGA officers were invited to meetings and training, they often could not attend.
445 The poor coordination between the state and LGA levels was perceived to be manifest in a lack

446 of relationship between the VEAs of the ADPs and the LGA or LGA extension agents.
447 Although they had similar roles, each extension agent group was reported to do their work in
448 isolation. Key informants confirmed the poor LGA funding at that level. It was highlighted that
449 LGA extension agents often could not get much done because there were no funds for
450 transportation to visit farming families. The LGA level likewise confirmed that coordination
451 between their level and the state level was poor. Instances were recounted where the LGA
452 officers received information from community leaders about the state officers conducting
453 activities in the communities without involving the LGA or asking for their input.

454 Regarding multisectoral coordination structures, it was reported that the NCFN had been
455 inactive for several years because of human resource capacity gaps within the National
456 Planning Commission, leading to an inability to convene meetings and facilitate coordination
457 of nutrition activities. Moreover, there had also been challenges with getting funding to conduct
458 the activities of the NCFN. Key informants further highlighted that it was not clear whether
459 many of the SCFN and LGCFN were functional and that the common state of inactivity
460 reported challenged the basic notion of the existence of these coordination mechanisms.

461 **Stakeholders' reactions to study findings**

462 Participants who reviewed the findings and subsequent recommendations from the study
463 agreed with the findings and emphasised the need for better stakeholder coordination.
464 However, the participants discounted co-location as a potential coordination approach for
465 Nigeria, highlighting that a concentration of stakeholders in some geographic locations will
466 mean neglect of other areas. Participants also perceived that co-location could lead to reduced
467 funding for each implementing organisation because they would be expected to leverage the
468 activities of others rather than directly implementing all activities.

469 **Discussion**

470 This study aimed to identify the stakeholders, interventions and coordination mechanisms for
471 NSA in Nigeria to facilitate improved coherence, consistency, synergy, scale, impact and
472 accountability among stakeholders. The study's main findings were that a considerable number
473 of active stakeholders with agricultural interventions had the potential to address nutrition.
474 However, nutrition potential was yet to be harnessed/maximised, evidenced by inadequate
475 inclusion of nutrition objectives, activities and indicators in the interventions. Existing
476 interventions differed across states and LGAs, and coordination within the agriculture sector
477 and between this sector and other sectors was limited. Inadequate/ineffective political will,
478 information sharing, trust, funding, and human resources at all levels of government were
479 significant challenges to the implementation and coordination of NSA.

480 The findings from this study are not peculiar to Nigeria. The limited nutrition sensitivity of
481 agricultural interventions has been previously documented.^{24,53,54} The identified
482 implementation and coordination challenges are also similar to what has been reported in other
483 countries in Africa and Asia.²⁰⁻²⁵ In fact, these reported experiences from other countries
484 indicate that the currently limited implementation of the AFSNS is not surprising given the
485 situation with stakeholder NSA approaches, relationships and coordination in 2015. Reviewing
486 the findings of our study in the light of the lessons learned from these other countries,²⁰⁻²⁵ some
487 of which have implemented successful NSA interventions,²⁵ suggests several actions that can
488 improve the enabling environment for NSA in Nigeria.

489 First, there is a need to address and improve nutrition literacy among NSA stakeholders.^{20,21,55}
490 The limited inclusion of nutrition objectives, activities and indicators in agricultural
491 interventions and the perception among stakeholders that improved food security will
492 automatically lead to improved nutrition highlights a need for NSA stakeholders to better

493 understand what NSA is and how to achieve it. As part of nutrition literacy activities, it would
494 be necessary to ensure that stakeholders reach a consensus around a common conceptual
495 framework of the links between agriculture and nutrition and subsequently agree on the roles
496 of different stakeholders in addressing these links.^{22,23}

497 Next, intrasectoral (horizontal and vertical) and multisectoral coordination must improve
498 among stakeholders. Previous reports have documented that the agriculture, nutrition and
499 health sectors will need to work closely together on intervention design, implementation and
500 evaluation if agriculture is to have a meaningful and lasting impact on nutrition and health.^{20–}
501 ^{25,56} The findings of our study emphasise the need to improve the relationship between FMARD
502 MDAs and all actors in the agricultural sector and improvements in multisectoral coordination.
503 The role definition already mentioned is essential for improving coordination.²⁴ However, role
504 definition must protect sectoral interests and autonomy to be effective.¹⁵ Given that institutional
505 turf battles and duplication of efforts were emphasised as critical challenges to implementing
506 nutrition-sensitive action, improving coordination may require FMARD to take a supportive
507 rather than lead role for actions already being implemented by other MDAs.

508 Further, the multisectoral activities included in the AFSNS and the responsibility of lead
509 agency assigned to FMARD²⁷ indicate that the AFSNS implicitly assumes an integration
510 approach to coordination. However, an integrated approach has been reported to be ineffective
511 for nutrition interventions in contexts like Nigeria, where MDAs have a sectoral mandate,
512 resource allocation is done through MDAs, and the technical expertise of implementing officers
513 is sectoral.^{9,10,15–18} Co-location has been suggested as a viable alternative to integration in such
514 situations,^{15–18} but will need to be contextually tested.¹⁶ Nevertheless, the resistance to co-
515 location by participants who reviewed the study's findings emphasises a need for increased
516 stakeholder engagement, dialogue and consensus.

517 Stakeholder engagement is more effective when centred on a stakeholder engagement plan that
518 articulates the purpose of engagement and the extent to which each group of stakeholders is to
519 be engaged at every stage of an intervention.^{13,14} Engagement can occur at about five different
520 levels: 1) information sharing (little opportunity to receive stakeholder feedback); 2)
521 consultation (stakeholders proffer opinions for consideration in decision making); 3)
522 participation (stakeholders participate in decision making); 4) negotiation/partnerships
523 (stakeholders combine expertise and resources to achieve a common goal); and 5)
524 empowerment (stakeholders can make operational decisions and own intervention). The extent
525 to which a stakeholder should be engaged depends on the perceived level of their influence
526 over the success of an intervention.¹³ For instance, state and LGA stakeholders who are crucial
527 to implementing an intervention can be engaged at the level of empowerment. In contrast,
528 stakeholders such as NGOs who work independently in the intervention location can be
529 engaged at the level of consultation. Furthermore, FMARD MDAs that are not directly
530 involved in an intervention can be engaged in information sharing. The intervention stage can
531 also influence the level of engagement that is done. For example, FMARD can engage FMOH
532 at the level of participation at an intervention design stage but only at the level of information
533 sharing in the implementation stage. Effective stakeholder engagement requires time and
534 resources that must be adequately budgeted for. Higher levels of engagement should also be
535 budgeted for and conducted before lower levels.^{13,14}

536 Regarding the capacity of stakeholders (especially government MDAs) to implement NSA
537 interventions, lessons from other countries indicate that partnerships between government and
538 NGOs can address both shortages in the number of human resources and knowledge and skill
539 gaps.²⁵ Other authors have emphasised the need to build capacity among personnel at multiple
540 levels (top-, mid-, and bottom levels) and through both in-service as well as pre-service
541 trainings.⁵⁵

542 Our study had several strengths, but also some limitations. One strength is that data were
543 collected using multiple approaches (document gathering and review, interviews, and FGDs)
544 and were triangulated. Another strength is that key informants across various types of
545 organizations and levels of government were interviewed, increasing the ability of the study to
546 identify a comprehensive list of relevant stakeholders. Thirdly, data saturation was reached
547 regarding the enablers and challenges of NSA in Nigeria as the same issues were emphasized
548 by the different data sources and interviewees.

549 Limitations of the study include the small number of key informants interviewed and the small
550 number of organizations and states/LGAs from which informants were recruited. As reported
551 in the study, it is possible that some relevant stakeholders and interventions were missed due
552 to the small sample size of interviewees. Secondly, some organizations and individuals
553 declined to grant interviews. This refusal could have created a potential situation in which the
554 findings from the study were systematically biased because of unidentified systematic
555 differences between the characteristics of those who consented to be interviewed versus those
556 who did not consent. Moreover, some interviewees were reluctant to respond to questions about
557 interventions and organizational activities (reflecting the information hoarding identified as an
558 NSA challenge). These limitations led to incomplete information mapping (Supplemental
559 Material 2) and an inability to completely separate situations in which information about
560 interventions (e.g., nutrition activities) simply did not exist, from situations in which
561 information existed but was not obtained in the course of data collection.

562 **Conclusion**

563 Several groups of stakeholders were involved in implementing nutrition-sensitive agriculture
564 interventions in Nigeria in 2015. These groups are government MDAs, INGOs, Nigerian NGOs
565 and other organisations, the UN system, bilateral agencies, research organisations and funding

566 organisations. In the descriptions accessible for nearly all NSA interventions identified, the
567 nutrition goals and activities and/or indicators to measure outcomes were not clearly
568 communicated. Also, there appeared to be minimal cross-sectoral partnerships formed.
569 Previous literature indicates that multisectoral collaboration between the agriculture, nutrition,
570 and health sectors is necessary for agricultural interventions to have any meaningful impact on
571 nutrition. Our study found that multisectoral collaboration was challenging because of mistrust,
572 rivalry and battles over institutional turf. The Agricultural Sector Food Security and Nutrition
573 Strategy (AFSNS) developed to guide NSA interventions across the country assumed an
574 integration approach to coordination. Yet, evidence from other countries suggests that a co-
575 location approach will be more effective in the Nigerian context.

576 Addressing challenges with NSA stakeholder relationships and coordination in Nigeria
577 requires improved nutrition literacy among stakeholders and stakeholder engagement
578 facilitated by role definition, clarification, and consensus. Stakeholder engagement needs to
579 occur at several levels depending on the influence each stakeholder has over the success of
580 various components of interventions. Effective engagement will foster trust among
581 stakeholders, increase productivity and minimise inefficiencies.

582

583 **Acknowledgements**

584 The original study was conceptualized and/or designed by Victor Ajieroh, Larry Ummuna,
585 Francis Aminu, and Olutayo Adeyemi. Data collection and analysis was performed by Olutayo
586 Adeyemi. The development of the manuscript from the original research was undertaken by
587 Adeyinka Onabolu, Victor Ajieroh, and Olutayo Adeyemi. All authors commented on previous
588 versions of the manuscript and approved the final manuscript.

589 **References**

- 590 1. Brugha R, Varvasovszky Z. Stakeholder analysis: a review. *Health Policy Plan.*
591 2000;15(3):239-246.
- 592 2. Rochefort DA, Cobb RW. Problem definition: An emerging perspective. In: Rochefort
593 DA, Cobb RW, eds. *The politics of problem definition: Shaping the policy agenda.*
594 Lawrence, KS: University Press of Kansas; 1994:1-31.
- 595 3. Black N. Evidence based policy: proceed with care. *BMJ (Clinical research ed).*
596 2001;323(7307):275-279.
- 597 4. AbouZahr C, Adjei S, Kanchanachitra C. From data to policy: good practices and
598 cautionary tales. *The Lancet.* 2007;369(9566):1039-1046.
- 599 5. Grindle MS, Thomas JW. *Public Choices and Policy Change: The Political Economy of*
600 *Reform in Developing Countries.* Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press; 1991.
- 601 6. Walt G, Gilson L. Reforming the health sector in developing countries: the central role of
602 policy analysis. *Health Policy Plan.* 1994;9(4):353-370.
- 603 7. Blanchet K, James P. How to do (or not to do) a social network analysis in health systems
604 research. *Health Policy Plan.* 2012;27(5):438-446.
- 605 8. Gillespie S, Haddad L, Mannar V, et al. The politics of reducing malnutrition: building
606 commitment and accelerating progress. *The Lancet.* 2013;382(9891):552-569.
- 607 9. Benson T. Improving nutrition as a development priority. *Addressing undernutrition in*
608 *national policy processes in sub-Saharan Africa* Washington, DC: *International Food*
609 *Policy Research Institute.* 2008.

- 610 10. Benson T. Cross-sectoral coordination in the public sector: A challenge to leveraging
611 agriculture for improving nutrition and health. *Edited by Shenggen Fan and Rajul*
612 *Pandya-Lorch*. 2011:145.
- 613 11. Morris SS, Cogill B, Uauy R, Maternal, Group CUS. Effective international action against
614 undernutrition: why has it proven so difficult and what can be done to accelerate progress?
615 *The Lancet*. 2008;371(9612):608-621.
- 616 12. Vachat ED. Sowing the Seeds of Good Nutrition: Making Agricultural Policies Deliver
617 Better Nutrition. *Paris: Action Contre la Faim (ACF)*. 2013.
- 618 13. GIIRS. *GIIRS Emerging Market Assessment Resource Guide: Stakeholder Engagement*.
619 [http://bimpactassessment.net/sites/all/themes/bcorp_impact/pdfs/em_stakeholder_engag](http://bimpactassessment.net/sites/all/themes/bcorp_impact/pdfs/em_stakeholder_engagement.pdf)
620 [ement.pdf](http://bimpactassessment.net/sites/all/themes/bcorp_impact/pdfs/em_stakeholder_engagement.pdf). Accessed February 24, 2022.
- 621 14. SustainAbility. *Practices and Principles for Successful Stakeholder Engagement*; 2007.
622 [https://fdocuments.net/document/sustainability-practices-and-principles-for-successful-](https://fdocuments.net/document/sustainability-practices-and-principles-for-successful-stakeholder-engagement.html)
623 [stakeholder-engagement.html](https://fdocuments.net/document/sustainability-practices-and-principles-for-successful-stakeholder-engagement.html). Accessed February 24, 2022.
- 624 15. Levinson FJ, Balarajan Y, Marini A. Addressing malnutrition multisectorally: what have
625 we learned from recent international experience. *New York: UNICEF and MDG*
626 *Achievement Fund*. 2013.
- 627 16. Di Prima S, Wright EP, Sharma IK, Syurina E, Broerse JE. Implementation and scale-up
628 of nutrition-sensitive agriculture in low-and middle-income countries: a systematic
629 review of what works, what doesn't work and why. *Global Food Security*.
630 2022;32:100595.
- 631 17. Heaver R. Improving nutrition: Issues in management and capacity development. 2002.

- 632 18. Alderman H, Elder L, Goyal A, et al. *Improving Nutrition through Multisectoral*
633 *Approaches*. World Bank; 2013.
- 634 19. Herforth A. Synthesis of guiding principles on agriculture programming for nutrition.
635 *Draft, September*. 2012.
- 636 20. Gillespie S, van den Bold M, Hodge J, Herforth A. Leveraging agriculture for nutrition
637 in South Asia and East Africa: examining the enabling environment through stakeholder
638 perceptions. *Food Security*. 2015;7(3):463-477.
- 639 21. van den Bold M, Kohli N, Gillespie S, Zuberi S, Rajeesh S, Chakraborty B. Is there an
640 enabling environment for nutrition-sensitive agriculture in South Asia? Stakeholder
641 perspectives from India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. *Food Nutri Bull*. 2015;36(2):231-247.
- 642 22. Gupte J, Longhurst R. How do the state's organisational capacities at the micro- and
643 macro-levels influence agriculture-nutrition linkages in fragile contexts? *Food Policy*.
644 2019;82:74-83. doi:10.1016/j.foodpol.2018.10.016
- 645 23. Gillespie S, Van Den Bold M, Hodge J. Nutrition and the governance of agri-food systems
646 in South Asia: A systematic review. *Food Policy*. 2019;82:13-27.
- 647 24. Gillespie S, Poole N, van den Bold M, Bhavani RV, Dangour AD, Shetty P. Leveraging
648 agriculture for nutrition in South Asia: What do we know, and what have we learned?
649 *Food Policy*. 2019;82:3-12.
- 650 25. Sharma IK, Essink D, Fumado V, Mridha MK, Bhattacharjee L, Broerse JE. What
651 Influences the Implementation and Sustainability of Nutrition-Sensitive Agriculture
652 Interventions? A Case Study from Southern Bangladesh. *Sustainability*.
653 2021;13(21):12049.

- 654 26. Akinyele IO. *Ensuring Food and Nutrition Security in Rural Nigeria: An Assessment of*
655 *the Challenges, Information Needs, and Analytical Capacity*. International Food Policy
656 Research Institute (IFPRI); 2009.
- 657 27. FMARD. *Nigeria Agricultural Sector Food Security and Nutrition Strategy*. Abuja,
658 Nigeria: Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development; 2017:107.
- 659 28. UNAS. *Improving Nutrition through Agriculture in Nigeria and Uganda: Needs,*
660 *Opportunities, Requirements and Strategies for the Future*. Kampala, Uganda: The
661 Uganda National Academy of Sciences (UNAS); 2011.
- 662 29. FMARD. *National Workshop on Mainstreaming Nutrition into Agricultural Policies,*
663 *Programmes and Value Chains, 27th – 28th August 2014*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal
664 Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development; 2014.
- 665 30. FMARD. *Agricultural Transformation Agenda Score Card 2013*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal
666 Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD); 2014.
- 667 31. Babu SC, Gyimah-Brempong K, Nwafor M, Edeh HO. *Capacity Assessment for*
668 *Achieving the Agricultural Transformation Agenda in Nigeria*. Vol Working Paper No.
669 26. Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI); 2014.
- 670 32. FMARD. *ECOWAP/CAADP Process National Agricultural Investment Plan (NAIP)*
671 *2010-2013*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal Republic of Nigeria; 2010.
- 672 33. MBNP. *National Policy on Food and Nutrition*. Abuja, Nigeria: Ministry of Budget and
673 National Planning (MBNP); 2016.
- 674 34. NPC. *National Policy on Food and Nutrition*. 1st ed. Abuja, Nigeria: National Planning
675 Commission (NPC); 2005.

- 676 35. (NPC) NPC. *National Plan of Action on Food and Nutrition in Nigeria*; 2004.
- 677 36. CRS. *Sustainable Mechanism for Improving Livelihoods and Household Empowerment*
678 *(SMILE): Program Quarterly Progress Report October - December 2014*. Abuja,
679 Nigeria: Catholic Relief Services (CRS); 2015.
- 680 37. ACF. *Annual Progress Report 2013*. ACF International; 2013.
681 [https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/sites/default/files/publications/ACF_Annual_Progr](https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/sites/default/files/publications/ACF_Annual_Progress_Report_2013.pdf)
682 [ess_Report_2013.pdf](https://www.actionagainsthunger.org/sites/default/files/publications/ACF_Annual_Progress_Report_2013.pdf).
- 683 38. ActionAid. *Take Action: End Poverty - Country*. Abuja, Nigeria: ActionAid Nigeria
- 684 39. DFID. *Operational Plan 2011 - 2016 Revised*. Abuja, Nigeria: Department for
685 International Development (DFID); 2014.
- 686 40. FMARD. *The Transformative Partnership for High Energy Nutritious Foods for Africa*
687 *(P4HNF): Strategy Blueprint & Implementation Plan*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal Ministry
688 of Agriculture and Rural Development; 2015.
- 689 41. FMAWR. *National Food Security Programme*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal Ministry of
690 Agriculture and Water Resources; 2008.
- 691 42. IFAD. *Federal Republic of Nigeria: Country Programme Evaluation*. International Fund
692 for Agricultural Development (IFAD); 2009.
- 693 43. IFAD. *Federal Republic of Nigeria: Country Strategic Opportunities Programme*. Rome:
694 International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD); 2010.

- 695 44. IFAD. *President's Report: Proposed Loan and Grant to the Federal Republic of Nigeria*
696 *for the Value Chain Development Programme*. Rome: International Fund for Agricultural
697 Development (IFAD); 2012.
- 698 45. SCI. *Tackling Child Malnutrition: Nigeria*. Save the Children (SCI); 2012.
- 699 46. SCI. *Social Protection and Child Malnutrition: Nigeria*. Save the Children (SCI); 2012.
- 700 47. New-Alliance. *Cooperation Framework to Support the New Alliance for Food Security*
701 *and Nutrition in Nigeria*. The New Alliance for Food Security and Nutrition in Africa;
702 2013.
- 703 48. New-Alliance. *New Alliance for Food Security and Nutrition Progress Report 2013-14*.
704 New Alliance for Food Security and Nutrition Africa; 2014.
- 705 49. AfDB. *Federal Republic of Nigeria Agricultural Transformation Agenda Support*
706 *Program - Phase I (ATASP-1)*. African Development Bank (AfDB); 2013.
- 707 50. FMAWR. *Third National Fadama Development Project (Fadama III): Project*
708 *Implementation Manual*. Abuja, Nigeria: Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Water
709 Resources; 2009.
- 710 51. WB. *Project Paper on a Proposed Additional Credit for the Third National Fadama*
711 *Development Project (Fadama III)*. World Bank; 2013.
- 712 52. IFAD. *Community-Based Natural Resource Management Programme (CBNRMP)*
713 *Supervision Report*. International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD); 2014.

- 714 53. Ruel MT, Alderman H, Maternal, Group CNS. Nutrition-sensitive interventions and
715 programmes: how can they help to accelerate progress in improving maternal and child
716 nutrition? *The Lancet*. 2013;382(9891):536-551.
- 717 54. Ruel MT, Quisumbing AR, Balagamwala M. Nutrition-sensitive agriculture: what have
718 we learned so far? *Glob Food Sec*. 2018;17:128-153.
- 719 55. Aryeetey R, Covic N. A Review of Leadership and Capacity Gaps in Nutrition-Sensitive
720 Agricultural Policies and Strategies for Selected Countries in Sub-Saharan Africa and
721 Asia. *Food Nutr Bull*. 2020;41(3):380-396.
- 722 56. Ved R, Menon P. Analyzing intersectoral convergence to improve child undernutrition in
723 India: Development and application of a framework to examine policies in agriculture,
724 health, and nutrition. 2012.

Table 1: Summary of Key Informants and Participants at FGDs

Type of Organisation	Sector	Number of Participants
<i>Interviews</i>		
Federal Government	Agriculture	6
Federal Government	Multisector	1
Development Partners (Donors and United Nations)	Multisector	2
International Nongovernmental Organisation	Multisector	4
International Research Institute	Agriculture	1
State Agricultural Development Programme	Agriculture	2 (1 each for North and South Nigeria)
Local Government Area Department of Agriculture	Agriculture	1 (North Nigeria)
<i>Focus Group Discussions</i>		
Federal Government	Agriculture	2 FGDs (3 – 4 participants from the same organisation per FGD)